

OPTIMIZING TOURIST SATISFACTION AT MOJOKERTO'S PACET SPECIAL MARKET THROUGH LOCATION, ATTRACTION AND SOCIAL MEDIA PROMOTION

Ardi Dwi Aditya¹, Sri Andayani², Ute Chairuz M. Nasutio³

^{1,2,3}University 17 August 1945 Surabaya

Email: ardi.dw685@gmail.com¹, sri@untag-sby.ac.id², uthe@untag-sby.ac.id³

Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received May 21, 2024 Revised May 22, 2024 Accepted May 30, 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Location, Attraction, Social Media Promotion, Tourist Satisfaction</p>	<p>This research aims to examine the influence of location, attractiveness and social media promotion on tourist satisfaction at Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto. Indonesia, with more than 17,540 islands and diverse cultural riches, is a popular tourist destination. In the first semester of 2023, 433.57 million domestic trips were recorded, with East Java contributing 116.7 million visits. Mojokerto Regency, especially Kramatjetak Village in Pacet District, has interesting tourism potential such as "Kramat Market". This research uses quantitative methods with Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. Data was obtained from 108 respondents via e-questionnaire. The research results show that Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion have a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction, both partially and simultaneously, with a determination value of 34.2%. The remaining 65.8% is influenced by other factors such as product quality, word of mouth, service quality and price.</p> <p style="text-align: right;">This is an open-access article under the CC-BY 4.0 license.</p>

Corresponding Author:

Author Name

Ardi Dwi Aditya

Email: ardi.dw685@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

This research aims to examine the influence of location, attractiveness and social media promotion on tourist satisfaction at Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto. Indonesia, with more than 17,540 islands and diverse cultural riches, is a popular tourist destination. In the first semester of 2023, 433.57 million domestic trips were recorded, with East Java contributing 116.7 million visits. Mojokerto Regency, especially Kramatjetak Village in Pacet District, has interesting tourism potential such as "Kramat Market" [1]. This

research uses quantitative methods with Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. Data was obtained from 108 respondents via e-questionnaire.

The research results show that Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion have a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction, both partially and simultaneously, with a determination value of 34.2%. The remaining 65.8% is influenced by other factors such as product quality, word of mouth, service quality and price [2]. Kramat Market, as a result of the community self-help movement, seeks to improve the economy by utilizing the environment, preserving culture, and protecting the local ecosystem. Founded in 2019, the market has developed into a significant tourist attraction [3].

Social media promotion plays an important role in introducing Pasar Keramat to a wider audience. With 150 million internet users in Indonesia actively using social media every day, this platform offers a great opportunity for the tourism sector to increase exposure and knowledge about tourist attractions [4]. TikTok, YouTube, and Facebook are the most popular platforms in Indonesia, providing opportunities for effective tourism marketing [5].

Keramat Market not only offers a unique shopping experience using wooden coins as a means of transaction, but also serves a variety of traditional Javanese food and bamboo crafts [6]. Continuous efforts in promotion and good management are expected to maintain the attractiveness of this market and preserve valuable cultural heritage for future generations. It is hoped that this research can become a reference for tourism managers and future researchers to continue developing the local tourism sector [7].

METHODS

This research design uses a quantitative model with descriptive methods to examine the influence of attraction, location and social media promotion on tourist satisfaction at Kramat Market, Pacet, Mojokerto. This research is based on the philosophy of positivism and uses research instruments such as a closed questionnaire with a Likert scale. Data collection was carried out via Google Form and direct interviews. The research population is all tourists who have visited Kramat Market, with a minimum sample of 108 respondents selected using purposive sampling techniques. The validity and reliability of the instrument were tested using the Product Moment and Spearman Brown correlation methods. Data were analyzed quantitatively using multiple linear regression and hypotheses were tested using SPSS. Data collection techniques also include direct observation and literature study. This research aims to provide an in-depth picture of how these variables influence tourist satisfaction, with a focus on accurate measurement and high data validity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Sacred Market in Pacet, Mojokerto, is a culinary and cultural tourism destination located in a bamboo garden that was a former rubbish dump. Only open twice a month on Sundays, this market offers a unique experience with an old-world atmosphere, where traders use bamboo to store their wares and traditional cooking

utensils. The food sold is traditional snacks such as horok-horok and dawet, served on a leaf base. Transactions use bamboo coins called gobok. The traders dress in traditional clothes, and this market also presents cultural performances as education for visitors.

Respondent Characteristics

In this research, the characteristics of respondents are an important aspect that influences the way they interpret and respond to questions in the questionnaire. The 108 respondents involved were dominated by women with a percentage of 55.6%, while men contributed 44.4%. In terms of age, the majority of respondents were in the 36-45 year range, indicating the dominance of this age group in their visits to Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto. In terms of employment, the majority of respondents are private employees (33.3%), which shows that this market is often visited by those looking for recreation on Sundays.

In terms of domicile, respondents came from various cities around Mojokerto, with Malang being the largest (32.4%), followed by Sidoarjo (27.8%) and Surabaya (17.6%). Income characteristics also varied, with the majority of respondents (43.52%) having income between IDR 3,000,000 to IDR 4,500,000 per month. Thus, this research illustrates that visitors to Pasar Keramat have diversity in their demographic and socio-economic aspects, which can influence their perceptions and satisfaction with this tourist destination.

Through this analysis, researchers can better understand the demographic profile of visitors to these markets and how these characteristics influence their perceptions and experiences when visiting local tourist destinations. By considering these factors, market managers and related parties can improve marketing and management strategies to meet the diverse needs and expectations of their visitors.

Validity test

Validity test is the ability of a measuring instrument to measure a respondent's questionnaire. An instrument is considered valid if the appropriate test t_{obs} on each questionnaire instrument. The instrument of the questionnaire is considered valid if $r_{count} > r_{table}$, in accordance with the validity test assessment requirements. The results of the validity test are displayed as follows below:

The results of the validity test concluded that each statement submitted for each Independent (free) variable, namely Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2), Social Media Promotion (X3) and the dependent (dependent) variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y). shows that all the indicators used to measure the variables used in this research have calculated r values $> r_{table}$. For a significance level of 0.05 or 5%, the r_{table} is 0.361. Based on the results of the validity test, all measurement indicators in the questionnaire are VALID.

Reliability Test

Reliability can be defined as the extent to which measurement results can be relied upon. The dependability of the questionnaire will be assessed to determine its level of reliability. The reliability test uses a limit of 0.60 as a decision making tool, a variable is considered reliable if its value shows Cronbach's Alpha > 0.60. The results of the reliability test are shown as follows in the table below:

Table 4.1 Reliable Test Results

Variable	Cronback Alpha	Alpha coefficient	Status
Location	0.863	0.60	REAL
Attractiveness	0.756	0.60	REAL
Social Media Promotion	0.638	0.60	REAL
Tourist Satisfaction	0.644	0.60	REAL

Source: Processed by the Author (2024)

Based on the results of the reliability test in the above table using the Cronbach Alpha (α) statistical test, it shows that all variables have a Cronbach Alpha > 0.60. This shows that the questionnaire used to measure the variables Location, Attractiveness, Social Media Promotion, and Tourist satisfaction is a blessing.

Data Tabulation

Based on the tabulation results of respondent data on the variables location (X1), tourist attraction (X2), and social media promotion (X3) at the Keramat Pacet Market, Mojokerto, it appears that the majority of respondents showed a significant level of agreement with the influence of location, tourist attraction, and social media promotion of their satisfaction as tourists. The average scores obtained were 3.41 for location, 3.55 for tourist attraction, and 3.4 for social media promotion. This shows that these aspects play an important role in influencing visitor satisfaction at the destination, with an overall tourist satisfaction score reaching an average of 3.12. This analysis provides an overview of the factors that need to be considered in improving tourist experience and satisfaction at the Pacet Keramat Market.

Variable Tabulation Average Analysis

This research used 108 respondents by distributing questionnaires, the answers to the questionnaire data used a Likert scale frequency on each scale using an intervention method. The scale used to measure respondents' responses consists of 5 (five scales), namely:

$$\text{Panjang Kelas Interval} = \frac{\text{Rentang}}{\text{Banyak Kelas}}$$

$$\text{Panjang Kelas Interval} = \frac{5 - 1}{5} = 0,8$$

So, a score interpretation scale is obtained from the average of respondents' answers with the following scale range:

Table 4.2 Average Score Interval

Intervals	Alternative Answers
1.00 – 1.79	Strongly Disagree (STS)
1.80 – 2.59	Disagree (TS)
2.60 – 3.39	Disagree (KS)
3.40 – 4.19	Agree (S)
4.20 – 5.00	Strongly Agree (SS)

Analysis of the tabulated average of respondents' answers shows variability in perceptions of Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto. The market location was considered strategic by respondents with the highest average score of 3.66, however the comfort of the prayer room received a lower rating with an average of 2.92. Tourist attractions such as memorable experiences from the uniqueness of this place were recognized with an average of 3.44, while natural beauty as the main attraction only got 1.86. Promotion via social media was considered effective with an average score of 4.27, although promotional messages that motivated further exploration only received 2.44. Tourist satisfaction with services is generally positive with the highest average value of 3.73, however dissatisfaction regarding supporting facilities appears with an average of 2.60.

Recapitulation Tabulation of Respondents' Answers Based on the Highest Mean Value of All Variables

Table 4.3 Average Tabulation Results

NO	VARIABLES	MEANS	QUESTION
1	Environment (X1)	3.66	I think the location of Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto. Very strategic where local people do a lot of activities (selling, farming, gardening)
2	Uniqueness/Souvenirs (X2)	3.46	In my opinion, the uniqueness of Pacet Keramat Market, Mojokerto provides a memorable experience
3	Promotion Reach (X3)	4.27	I found out about Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto through social media
4	<i>Willingness to Recommend (Y)</i>	3.73	I advise friends or relatives to visit and buy the products offered by Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto because of the satisfactory service.

Source: Processed by the Author (2024)

Data Analysis

Classic assumption test

Normality test

The aim of the normity test is to find out whether the data distribution of a set of data or variables is normally distributed or not.[10]. The norm test is one of the tests carried out as a prerequisite before starting data processing. The norm test is carried out before carrying out data processing using the proposed research mode. Finding the distribution of data in a variable that will be used in research is the goal of the data norm test. Data that is normally distributed is good and practical to support these research modes.[11]. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used in testing the norm of this research, and meets the following requirements. The residual value is said to have a normal distribution if the residual significance value is > 0.05 . It can be said that the residual value is normally distributed. Preferably, the residual value is considered not to be normally distributed if the residual significance value is < 0.05 .

One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test			
		Unstandardized Residual	
N	108		
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	0,0000000	
	Std. Deviation	2,94466496	
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	0,053	
	Positive	0,040	
	Negative	-0,053	
Test Statistic	0,053		
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) ^c	.200 ^d		
Monte Carlo Sig. (2-tailed) ^e	Sig.	0,638	
	99% Confidence Interval	Lower Bound	0,625
		Upper Bound	0,650
a. Test distribution is Normal.			
b. Calculated from data.			
c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.			
d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.			
e. Lilliefors' method based on 10000 Monte Carlo samples with starting seed			

Figure 4.1 One Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test Results

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

From the table above, based on the results of the normality test, the Asymp Sig (2-tailed) value. Shows a result of 0.200d. From these results, the Asymp Sig (2-tailed) value is greater than > 0.05 , it can be concluded that the residual value is distributed normally.

This research also uses a data normality test via the histogram method and the P-Piot norm graph method.

Figure 4.2 Normality Test Results (Histogram)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

In the picture above, the norm test using the histogram method produces an upward curve. It can be said that the pattern has a normal distribution and the regression meets the assumption of normality.

Figure 4.3 Normality Results (P-Plot)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

In the picture above of the normality test with the P-Plot mode, it can be seen that the points follow and approach the diagonal line so it can be concluded that the regression meets the normality assumption.

Multicollinearity Test

The principle of linearity is a "perfect" or exact linear correlation between the explanatory variables entered into the model. According to Ghozali (2012: 105) in [12] The multicollinearity test aims to test whether a regression model has correlation. The

Multicollinearity test aims to test whether a regression model has correlation between independent variables. A good regression mode should not have correlation between independent variables. Testing the risk of linearity is seen from the amount of VIF (Variance Inflation Factor) and tolerance. Tolerance measures selected independent variables that are not explained by other independent variables. So a low tolerance value is the same as a high VIF value (because $VIF = 1/tolerance$). The cutoff value that is commonly used to indicate the risk of linearity is a tolerance value ≥ 0.10 , then there is a risk of linearity. If the tolerance value ≤ 0.10 then there is no risk of linearity, if the VIF value < 10.00 then there is no risk of linearity and if the VIF value > 10.00 then there is a risk of linearity.

Coefficients ^a							
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	9,526	2,412		3,949	0,000	
	Lokasi	0,193	0,091	0,230	2,128	0,036	0,544 1,840
	Daya Tarik	0,236	0,115	0,241	2,059	0,042	0,460 2,172
	Promosi Media Sosial	0,197	0,089	0,220	2,224	0,028	0,649 1,542

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Wisatawan

Figure 4.4 Multicollinearity Test Results
Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the output table above. The Tolerance value of the Location variable (X1) is 0.544. The Attraction variable (X2) is 0.460, and the Social Media Promotion variable (X3) is 0.649 which is greater than 0.10 while the VIF value of the Location variable (X1) is 1.840, the Attraction variable (X2) of 2.172 and the Social Media Promotion variable (X3) of 1.542 is smaller than 10.00, so it can be concluded that there is no Multicollinearity.

Heteroscedasticity Test

The test method for a regression model that assesses the inequality of variance between residuals from different observations is the heteroscedasticity test. It is called homoscedasticity if the residual variance remains from one observation to the next, and heteroscedasticity if it varies. A good regression mode is one that is homoscedastic or does not have heteroscedasticity problems. According to Ghosali (2013) in [13]. The purpose of the heteroscedasticity test is to ascertain whether there is an inequality of variance from the residuals of one observation to another observation in the regression mode." Because cross-section data captures data representing various sizes (small, medium, and large), most of the data contains heteroscedasticity scenarios.

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1,612	2,058		0,783	0,435
	Lokasi (X1)	-0,031	0,032	-0,096	-0,978	0,330
	Daya Tarik (X2)	0,055	0,053	0,107	1,037	0,302
	Promosi Media Sosial (X3)	-0,009	0,050	-0,018	-0,177	0,860

a. Dependent Variable: RES_2

Figure 4.5 Heteroscedasticity Test Results

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the results of the table, using the heteroscedastic test method using the Geljser correlation coefficient, it can be seen that the Location variable (X1) has a significance value of 0.330 and the Attractiveness variable (X2) has a significant value of 0.302 and Social Media Promotion (X3) has a significance value of 0.860 which is higher. greater than 0.05. And it can be said that heteroscedasticity does not occur.

Figure 4.6 Heteroscedasticity Test Results (Scatterplot)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the data table above, using the heteroscedasticity test with the scatterplot method, the determination of the heteroscedasticity test is that the points do not form a regular pattern that is clearly visible and only at one point. It can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity problem in the regression mode of the influence of Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2), and Social Media Promotion (X3) on Tourist Satisfaction (Y). so that the heteroscedacity test using scatterplot is fulfilled.

Linearity Test

The purpose of the linearity test is to ascertain whether there is a linear relationship between two or more variables being studied. Usually, linear regression or correlation

analysis uses this test as a prerequisite. The purpose of the linearity test is to ascertain whether there is a linear relationship between two or more variables being studied. This test is usually used as a requirement for linear regression or correlation analysis. In this test, it determines how a variable (X) Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2), Social Media Promotion (X3) affects the variable (Y) Tourist Satisfaction.

1) Linearity Test of the Location variable (X1) on the Tourist Satisfaction variable (Y)

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Kepuasan Wisatawan (Y) * Lokasi (X1)	Between Groups	(Combined)	233,969	19	12,314	0,955	0,520
		Linearity	46,678	1	46,678	3,620	0,060
		Deviation from Linearity	187,291	18	10,405	0,807	0,687
	Within Groups		1134,577	88	12,893		
	Total		1368,546	107			

Figure 4.7 Location Variable Linearity Test Results (Anova Table)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the table above, the results of the linearity test output are known to be Sig. Deviation From Linearity is $0.687 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that between the location variable (X1) and the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) there is a linear relationship.

2) Linearity Test of the Attraction variable (X2) on the Tourist Satisfaction variable (Y)

ANOVA Table							
			Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Kepuasan Wisatawan (Y) * Daya Tarik (X2)	Between Groups	(Combined)	395,833	15	26,389	2,496	0,004
		Linearity	196,705	1	196,705	18,604	0,000
		Deviation from Linearity	199,128	14	14,223	1,345	0,197
	Within Groups		972,714	92	10,573		
	Total		1368,546	107			

Figure 4.8 Linearity Test Results for Attractiveness Variables (Anova Table)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the table above, the results of the linearity test output are known to be Sig. Deviation From Linearity is $0.197 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that between the variable Attraction (X2) and the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) there is a linear relationship

3) Linearity Test of the Social Media Promotion variable (X3) on the Tourist Satisfaction variable (Y)

ANOVA Table						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Kepuasan Wisatawan (Y) * Promosi Media Sosial (X3)	Between Groups	(Combined) 435,513	16	27,220	2,655	0,002
		Linearity 286,561	1	286,561	27,949	0,000
		Deviation from Linearity 148,952	15	9,930	0,968	0,494
	Within Groups	933,033	91	10,253		
Total		1368,546	107			

Figure 4.9 Linearity Test Results for Social Media Promotion Variables (Anova Table)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the table above, the results of the linearity test output are known to be Sig. Deviation From Linearity is $0.494 > 0.05$, so it can be concluded that between the variable Social Media Promotion (X3) and the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) there is a linear relationship

Multiple Linear Test

By using a multiple linear regression test, it is used to test the truth of the research hypothesis, independent (free) variables against dependent (bound) variables. The following is a regression analysis of the influence of Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2), Social Media Promotion (X3) on Tourist Satisfaction (Y).

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	9.526	2.412		3.949	<,001
	Lokasi	.193	.091	.230	2.128	.036
	Daya Tarik	.236	.115	.241	2.059	.042
	Promosi Media Sosial	.197	.089	.220	2.224	.028

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Wisatawan

Figure 4.10 Multiple Linear Test Results

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the results of the linear regression, the following equation can be created:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + e$$

$$Y = 9.526 + 0.193(X_1) + 0.236(X_2) + 0.197(X_3)$$

Information :

Y = Tourist Satisfaction Variable

α = Constant

β_1 = Regression Coefficient from Location

β_2 = Regression Coefficient of Attractiveness

β_3 = Regression Coefficient from Social Media Promotion

X1 = Location Variable

X2 = Attraction Variable

X3 = Social Media Promotion Variable

e = tram error

From the regression equation it can be interpreted as follows:

- 1) The constanta (α) value obtained is 9.526 so it can be interpreted that if the independent variables (Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2) and Social Media Promotion) have a value of 0 (constant) then the dependent variable Purchase Satisfaction (Y) has a value of 9.526
- 2) $\beta_1(X1) = 0.193$, meaning that the regression coefficient value for the Location variable is 0.193, meaning that if the Location variable changes one unit, then Tourist Satisfaction will change by 0.193. The positive sign on the regression coefficient value indicates a unidirectional relationship between Tourist Satisfaction and Location, meaning that if Location increases, Tourist Satisfaction will also increase. Meanwhile, every time a tourism manager reduces the location, it will also be accompanied by a decrease in tourist satisfaction
- 3) $\beta_2(X2) = 0.236$, meaning that the regression coefficient value for the Attraction variable is 0.236, meaning that if the Attraction variable changes one unit, then Tourist Satisfaction will change by 0.236. The positive sign on the regression coefficient value indicates a unidirectional relationship between Tourist Satisfaction and Attraction, meaning that if Attraction increases, Tourist Satisfaction will also increase. Meanwhile, every decrease in Attractiveness that market managers carry out will also be accompanied by a decrease in Tourist Satisfaction.
- 4) $\beta_3(X3) = 0.197$, meaning that the regression coefficient value for the Social Media Promotion variable is 0.197, meaning that if the Social Media Promotion variable changes one unit, then Tourist Satisfaction will change by 0.197. The positive sign on the regression coefficient value indicates a unidirectional relationship between Tourist Satisfaction and Social Media Promotion, meaning that if Social Media Promotion increases, then Tourist Satisfaction will also increase. Meanwhile,

every decrease in Social Media Promotion carried out by market managers will also be accompanied by a decrease in Tourist Satisfaction.

Hypothesis testing

t Test (Partial Test)

The t test (partial test) was carried out to test the influence of the independent variables (Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion) on the dependent variable (Tourist Satisfaction) with a significance level of 0.05. Based on the test results, the calculated t value for Location is 2.128, Attractiveness is 2.059, and Social Media Promotion is 2.224, all of which are greater than the t table value (1.659). Therefore, the alternative hypothesis (Ha) is accepted for all variables: Location, Attraction, and Social Media Promotion have a positive and significant influence on Tourist Satisfaction at Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto. These results indicate that these factors contribute to increasing tourist satisfaction at that location.

F Test (Simultaneous)

The influence of independent variables working simultaneously on the dependent variable is examined using the simulated F test. The F test has degrees of freedom $df = nk - 1$ and a significance level of 0.05. The criteria used in the f test are as follows:

1. If the calculated F is less than F Table at $\alpha 0.05$, then Ho is rejected
2. If the calculated F is greater than F Table at $\alpha 0.05$, then Ho is accepted

ANOVAa						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	222,140	3	74,047	18,044	<.001b
	Residual	426,777	104	4,104		
	Total	648,917	107			
a. Dependent Variable: Tourist Satisfaction						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Social Media Promotion, Location, Attractiveness						

Figure 4.11F Test Results (Simultaneous)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

The formula for the table above is as follows:

$df = n - k - 1$

information :

k (Number of independent variables) = 3

n (Number of samples) = 108

df 1 = dknumerator = (k) = 3

df 2 = dkdenominator = nk-1 = 108 - 3 - 1

= 104

df = (3 : 104)

Fourth Hypothesis

Ho : There is no positive and significant influence of Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Keramat Pacet Market, Mojokerto

Ha : There is a positive and significant influence of Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Keramat Pacet Market, Mojokerto

Based on the table above, the sig value is known. for the influence of X1, towards Y.

3.1.1. Test R2

This R2 test aims to determine the contribution of the independent variables Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2) and Social Media Promotion (X3) together to the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y). The results of this test are shown by the R Square number which can be seen in the table.

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.585a	0.342	0.323	2.02574
a. Predictors: (Constant), Location, Attraction, Social Media Promotion				

Figure 4.12R2 Test Results (Determinant)

Source: Primary Data (Researcher)

Based on the table above with the Model Summary output results, it can be seen that the R² number is 0.342 or 34.2% of the R Square results or coefficient of determination. So it shows that the influence of the independent variables Location (X1), Attractiveness

(X2) and Social Media Promotion (X3) has an influence on the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y) which is 0.342 or 34.2%. While the rest (100% -34.2% = 65.8%). So with a value of 65.8% there are other variables that contribute quite a lot which were not studied by researchers, because the variables studied only contributed 34.2% and the remaining 65.8% came from outside variables in previous research such as the variables Facilities, Security, Culinary Tourism, Product Variations, Words of Mouth, Quality of Service, and Price.

Discussion

The aim of this research is to test the influence of Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Keramat Pacet Market, Mojokerto. The discussion of the research results is as follows:

The Influence of Location on Tourist Satisfaction at Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto

Based on the presentation of the results of the research analysis, it can be stated that location has a positive and significant influence on tourist satisfaction at the Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto. This can be proven by the results of the t test analysis in this study. In terms of the influence of the Location variable on Tourist Satisfaction, he explained that "According to respondents, the location of the Pacet Keramat Market, Mojokerto is very strategic where the local community has a lot of activities (selling, farming, gardening)." Respondents gave an agreeable assessment because there was still a lot of activity in the object's environment.

The results of this research are in accordance with research Ahmad Saputra (2015) with research on the Influence of Location, Product Quality and Service Quality on Consumer Satisfaction in Traditional Markets (case study of traditional markets in Medan Johor sub-district) provides the meaning that location is a factor that plays a very important role as a basis for respondents who feel satisfied when visiting. The location of this market still has many activities carried out by local residents, it is easy to reach by public transportation, can be seen clearly from the main road, is convenient for buying and selling transactions, and the regulations for managing this market so that it is better are key factors in the impression that respondents will feel. while at the object location.

The Influence of Attraction on Tourist Satisfaction at Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto

Based on the presentation of the results of the research analysis, it can be stated that Attraction has a positive and significant influence on Tourist Satisfaction at the Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto. This can be proven by the results of the t test analysis in this study. In terms of the influence of the Attractiveness variable on Tourist Satisfaction, he explained that "According to respondents, the uniqueness of the Pacet Keramat Market, Mojokerto provides a memorable experience." Respondents gave an affirmative

assessment because the attraction given to the object of this research provided a memorable experience like the atmosphere of the past. There are many unique things, food and souvenirs that are rarely found in the respondent's domicile.

The results of this research are in accordance with Malikhatun's research. et al (2020) in research on the Influence of Tourist Attractions, Tourist Culinary, and Tourist Satisfaction on Intention to Return to the Slumpring Market Tourist Object, Cempaka Village, District. It means that the strong attractiveness of a tourist attraction plays a role in increasing visitor satisfaction, because the quality and uniqueness of the object not only directly influences the tourist experience, but also enriches and broadens visitors' perspectives on the destination they visit, creating a deep and satisfying impression. on their journey.

The Influence of Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto

Based on the presentation of the research analysis, it can be stated that Social Media Promotion has a positive and significant influence on Tourist Satisfaction at the Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto. This can be proven by the results of the t test analysis in the research. In the influence of the Social Media Promotion variable on Tourist Satisfaction, explains that 'Respondents learned about Pasar Keramat Pacet, Mojokerto through social media Respondents gave an affirmative assessment because there was promotion through social media for this artificial tourism which was managed by local residents so that it developed and lasted a long time and also had a wide reach, many visited from several domiciles outside Mojokerto.

The results of this research are in accordance with research by Amei Riska Nandita and Kumara Adji Kusuma (2023) on research on the influence of social media, tourist facilities, service quality and security on tourist satisfaction among visitors to Legok Asri Sukolegok in Sidoarjo. Providing meaning that social media promotion has proven a very important role in influencing the level of tourist satisfaction with tourist attractions, because of its ability to widely reach and inform respondents about the uniqueness, facilities and experiences offered by the destination. Through these platforms (Youtube, Instagram, Tiktok, Twitter, etc.), visitors can easily find the latest information, reviews, and experiences of other people who have visited the place, which directly influences their perceptions before and during the visit, and provides the opportunity to interact directly with related managers or communities to obtain additional information or recommendations.

The Influence of Location, Attraction, and Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto

Based on the research analysis presentation, in the F test the calculated F value is greater > than the F table, so the Alternative Hypothesis (Ha) is accepted because the variables

Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2) and Social Media Promotion (X3) simultaneously (together -sama) has a positive and significant effect on Tourist Satisfaction (Y). Then the results of the determination test output (R²) of the independent variables Location (X1), Attractiveness (X2) and Social Media Promotion (X3) have an influence on the dependent variable Tourist Satisfaction (Y). This can prove that tourist satisfaction can be influenced by location, attractiveness and social media promotion.

The results of this research are in accordance with research by Karlinda Anika RP (2020) on research on the influence of promotions, facilities and tourist attractions on the decision to visit Kampoeng Djawi Jombang tourism and research by Dewi Mariana, et al (2019) on research on the influence of location and facilities on tourist visitor satisfaction. Pacet Hot Springs in Mojokerto Regency. It means that the three main factors including strategic location, attractive attractions, and promotion via social media play an important role in determining the level of visitor satisfaction with artificial tourist attractions. This tourist environment is still filled with various activities of local residents which add color and uniqueness to visitors. Along the road, local residents are busy running small businesses, ranging from selling handicrafts, regional culinary specialties, easy affordable access not only increases the comfort of visitors but also facilitates better accessibility, allowing them to enjoy a hassle-free tourism experience. The unique and attractive appeal of a tourist attraction creates interest and positive expectations before visitors arrive, and provides a satisfying and unforgettable experience during their visit. Meanwhile, effective promotion through social media expands the reach of information about a tourist attraction, allowing potential visitors to obtain up-to-date information, reviews of previous visitors' experiences, and a clear picture of the facilities and activities on offer, all of which can influence their decision to visit and increase their level of satisfaction after the travel experience is complete

CONCLUSION

Research on 'The Influence of Location, Attraction and Social Media Promotion on Tourist Satisfaction at Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto' concludes that these three variables have a positive and significant effect on tourist satisfaction. Better locations, such as improved road access and signage, increase tourist numbers. The increased attractiveness by adding uniqueness and quality of service also attracts more visitors. Expanded social media promotion by increasing content makes this market more widely known. Simultaneously, these three variables have a significant effect on tourist satisfaction. Recommendations for market managers include providing worship facilities, utilizing natural water sources to add attraction, and holding workshops on biodiversity and nature conservation. Future researchers are expected to use these results as a comparison and add insight with different approaches to increase understanding of this topic.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aristotle et al., "Utilization of Social Media for Tourism Promotion and the Potential of Local Wisdom in Batu Putuk Village, Teluk Betung Barat District, Bandar Lampung City," *Buguh J. Pengabd. To. Mass.*, vol. 1, no. 4, pp. 31–38, 2021, doi: 10.23960/buguh.v1n4.238.
- [2] DN Liani and N. Rina, "Motives for Using Twitter Social Media (Quantitative Descriptive Study of Followers of the @EXOind Twitter Account)," *Horizon J. Hum. Bina Sarana Inform.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 63–67, 2020.
- [3] Slice, "[2023 EDITION] LATEST INDONESIAN SOCIAL MEDIA USER STATISTICS," 4 May.
- [4] S. Patadjenu, M. Sondang Silitonga, and A. Asropi, "COLLABORATIVE GOVERNANCE OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT OF LIKUPANG, NORTH MINAHASA DISTRICT Tourism Development Collaborative Governance of Likupang, North Minahasa Regency," *Indonesian Tourism.*, vol. 17, no. 1, pp. 23–48, 2023.
- [5] BP Statistics, "Indonesia's Domestic Tourism Recovery 2022," *Pussy Body. Stat. (BPS - Stat. Indonesia. Jl. Dr. Sutomo 6-8 Jakarta 10710 Indonesia.*, no. 33, 2023.
- [6] S. . NH Nuriyah. Arinta, Adnan. Muhammad, "Relations between Political Figures and the Segoro Agung Islamic Boarding School, Mojokerto Regency, East Java, 2018-2021," *J. Bus. Theory Pract.*, vol. 10, no. 2, p. 6, 2021.
- [7] N. Fio, "Nostalgic Old School Atmosphere at the Pacet Sacred Market, Mojokerto," 03 February, 2023.
- [8] L. Kristanti, "Once Considered Haunted, Mojokerto's Sacred Market Becomes an Alternative Tourism," *Tugujatim*, 2023.
- [9] R. Arfianty, "THE INFLUENCE OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE ON EMPLOYEE RETENTION WITH THE PERCEPTION OF ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE AT PT NIRWANA SEMESTA ABADI INDONESIA," *Management*, 2023.
- [10] Suliyanto, "Classical Normality Assumption Test," *Econ. Apply. Theory. App. with SPSS*, vol. 1, p. 69, 2011.
- [11] P. Lestari, "EFFECTIVENESS OF USE OF PROBLEM-BASED LEARNING MODELS IN CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION SUBJECTS AT WATES 5 STATE MIDDLE SCHOOL," *Educator. CITIZENSHIP*, 2014.
- [12] MT Gugus, "EFFECTIVENESS OF USE OF DROP BOX AND ELECTRONIC FILLING (E-FILLING) SYSTEM TO IMPROVE COMPLIANCE WITH REPORTING ANNUAL INCOME TAX SPT FOR INDIVIDUAL TAXPAYERS," *Fak. Econ.*, 2015.
- [13] L. Spada IndonesiaL, "MEETING 8 HETEROSKEDASTICITY TESTS."